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CASEE STUDY APPLIED TO TEXTILE INDUSTRY PRODUCTS

Version history

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The textile sector is a key cause of ongoing worldwide degradation of the environment, most notably through its production and consumption model, which involves high consumption of resources in a linear manner. Textile produces high emissions of carbon dioxide, with a significant proportion taking place outside European borders, particularly in Asia. It is a source of high volumes of significant waste, most of which is combusted—releasing toxic chemicals—and buried in unregulated landfill, contributing to increased degradation and depletion of the environment and its resources. Water consumption is a critical issue, including both 'blue water' (factory-used surface and groundwater) and 'green water' (precipitation stored in the ground for agricultural use in irrigation). In addition, the growing use of natural and animal fibres requires high use of lands, and producing synthetic ones poses a significant challenge in terms of its use of fossil fuels and high requirements for energy consumption.

A further environmental concern relates to the extensive use of chemicals in textile finishing and enhancement processes. It is evident that treatments such as easy-care finishes (which are designed to make fabrics wrinkle-resistant) and flame-retardant (FR) treatments frequently involve substances that have the potential to be detrimental to human health and ecosystems. A significant proportion of these chemicals, including formaldehyde-based resins and brominated flame retardants, are characterised by their persistence in the environment, bioaccumulation potential, and the potential for toxicity. The application and subsequent release of these substances into water and air during the production and utilisation phases pose significant risks, further amplifying the environmental footprint of the textile industry. Logistics and retail operations contribute to additional degradation of the environment in the distribution channel (Duhoux et al., 2022).

Due to its conventional linear model and high requirements for resources, in recent years, increased efforts have focused on implementing circular economy in the textile sector. Transition towards a circular economy is universally regarded as a key path towards increased worldwide sustainability and maximization of use of resources. The key objective of such a model is minimizing the creation of waste, reducing consumption of resources, and minimizing impact on the environment. Notably, transitioning towards a circular economy in the textile sector has been most effectively achieved through the use of recycled materials in producing clothes and creating collection and recycling programs for outgrown clothes.

Reverse logistics (RL) plays a key role in such a transformation, managing and coordinating goods' reverse flow from their final location to re-entering the value chain for value retrieval or proper disposal. All processes involved in re-use of goods and materials fall under RL, including product return, recycling, re-manufacturing, and disposal of waste. In the case of the textile value chain, RL enables reverse flow of textiles, semi-finished goods, and production residues, and therefore helps in transitioning towards a more circular business model. Nevertheless, in RL to

make a meaningful contribution towards increased sustainability, consideration must be taken of emissions generated through transportation in reverse logistics operations.

Apart from its key role in driving circularity, RL in the textile value chain is also determined by regulative requirements, specifically with regard to the challenge posed by the EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles (EU Commission, 2022). Adopted in March 2022 through a Circular Economy Package and in coordination with the European Green Deal, the European Commission's strategy aims at making the textile value chain more sustainable. All textiles entering the EU marketplace must, by 2030, be durable, capable of being repaired, and recycled, and fast fashion must be reduced through encouragement of circular approaches such as reuse and mending. One key mechanism for its achievement is through creating an Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) scheme for textiles in all EU Member States.

This research starts with a review of literature on the environmental impact of the textile and apparel industry, followed by an examination of how reverse logistics can support circular economy principles. The study then undertakes a critical analysis of the barriers to their implementation. Finally, the research adopts a case study approach to identifying potential alternative strategies to enhance efficiency and sustainability in an Italian textile company, Mascioni S.p.A., located in Lombardy Region.

AIM OF THE REPORT

The present study aims to analyse the role of reverse logistics in supporting the transition of the textile sector from a linear to a circular economy model, with a particular focus on the textile case study represented by Mascioni S.p.A. In line with Task 3.1.5 of the NODES flagship project, the research investigates the management of backward flows of materials and products at the end of their life cycle — including textiles, packaging, and production residues — to enable recovery, recycling, refurbishment, and reuse. The study pursues a threefold objective: first, to collect and synthesise scientific literature and best practices at the international level, identifying effective strategies and barriers in the implementation of reverse logistics systems; second, to assess the current state of reverse logistics processes through dialogue with industrial and logistics firms, focusing on key performance indicators (KPIs) related to efficiency, sustainability, and resource optimisation; third, to apply these insights to a case study of Mascioni S.p.A., proposing a redesign of its reverse logistics system that integrates innovative practices, explores evolutionary alternatives, and aligns with European policy frameworks for sustainable and circular textiles. By doing so, the study not only seeks to improve material recovery and energy efficiency within Mascioni's operations but also to contribute to the broader development of high-value-added, scalable reverse logistics models for the textile sector.

2. INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

To provide a comprehensive understanding of the circular transition in the textile sector, the literature review is structured into four sections. The first outlines the environmental impacts and structural dynamics of the textile industry, highlighting the unsustainable characteristics of its current linear model. The second explores the role of reverse logistics as a fundamental component in enabling circular practices, such as recycling, reuse, and waste valorisation. The third section examines the main barriers—organisational, financial, and policy-related—that hinder the effective implementation of reverse logistics and circular economy strategies. Finally, a fourth section focuses on RL in the military textile sector. All these sections form the analytical basis for the case study and proposed interventions.

2.1 THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY

The textile and apparel (T&A) sector, valued at between \$1.7 trillion and \$2.5 trillion, is the third largest manufacturing sector in the world, following technology and automotive (McKinsey, 2022; House of Commons Environmental Audit Committee, 2019). Despite its high growth, the sector has had significant damaging environmental consequences. Projected trends in current emissions mean that, in 2050, the T&A sector will contribute one-quarter of worldwide carbon emissions (MacArthur, 2017). Emissions in this sector will rise to about 3.3 billion tonnes of CO₂ each year, almost equivalent to all 28 countries in the European Union, at about 3.5 billion tonnes (House of Commons Environmental Audit Committee, 2019).

The most significant environmental issue arises from high pollution in the processes involved in producing clothes. Wet processing processes discharge untreated effluents with high concentrations of toxic chemicals, with significant detrimental consequences for environments (Alkaya & Demirer, 2014; Hasanbeigi & Price, 2015). In fact, processes involved in dyeing and treating clothes alone contribute 20% of worldwide water pollution in industries and contribute about 35% of marine microplastics, equivalent to about 190,000 tonnes per annum. In addition, about 92 million tonnes of cloth waste occur each year, including clothes thrown out, combusted, and unsold merchandise (Niinimäki et al., 2020; House of Commons Environmental Audit Committee, 2019). Wastewater is yet another form of waste, and it could require a treatment process. With freshwater sources drying out at an unprecedented level, water treatment and reuse have become a necessity at a worldwide level (Rahaman, 2024).

The fast fashion boom has immensely fuelled the problem of waste. Comparatively, in 2000, fast fashion companies increased apparel production by 50%, and in a single year, an additional 100 billion new clothes were produced worldwide (Gazzola et al., 2020). Production increased consumption and accelerated disposal, and with it, placed the apparel industry in the position of being the second-largest pollutant in the world, contributing 5% towards overall waste (House of Commons Environmental Audit Committee, 2019).

It is important to make a distinction between the different textile wastes, Huygens et al. (2023) identifies four categories: Post-industrial waste is defined as the textile residues that are produced during the manufacturing process of textile products and their raw materials. Pre-consumer waste originates at the retail level and encompasses items such as unsold garments or materials that are in excess of required quantities. Several factors contribute towards generating pre-consumer waste, including the complexity of apparel design, the nature of fabrics, and efficiency in production (Das et al., 2025). Post-consumer waste from household sources encompasses textiles that have been utilised and subsequently discarded by private individuals, typically following the conclusion of their functional lifespan. This exclusionary criterion is applied to items that are specifically collected for the purpose of reuse. Finally, post-consumer waste from non-household or commercial sources is defined as discarded textiles from commercial and industrial users, including but not limited to hotels, hospitals and the automotive sector. In Italy, the 24% of textile wastes derives from post-consumer households' sources, and 11% from non-household sources. The post-industrial accounts for the 35% and the pre-consumer only for the 6% (ETC CE, 2025).

2.2 REVERSE LOGISTICS

The circular economy is as a viable solution to the escalating waste crisis currently being experienced by the textile industry, with the implementation of strategies for the management of waste being embedded directly into production processes. This approach has been demonstrated to reduce waste and conserve resources, while also generating substantial economic benefits. The European Commission's 2015 circular economy policy underscores these advantages, underlining opportunities for innovative business models, increased production efficiency, and enhanced social inclusion. To achieve these objectives, textile companies must implement strategies to reduce pre-consumer waste, optimise manufacturing processes, and adopt closed-loop recycling systems. As regulatory frameworks evolve and consumer awareness of sustainability grows, the industry faces mounting pressure to transition towards more sustainable production models, ones that mitigate environmental impact while strengthening economic resilience (EU Commission, 2020; EU Commission, 2015).

In this context, Reverse Logistics (RL) assumes a pivotal role in facilitating the transition of the textile sector towards a circular model. RL is defined as the management of the flow of goods from their endpoint back into the value chain, facilitating value recovery, reuse, and responsible disposal (Smith et al., 2022). It encompasses a range of operations, including reverse flows, recycling, remanufacturing, and waste management. Specifically, in the context of the textile sector, RL facilitates the return, collection, and recycling of production residues, intermediate goods, and fabrics, thereby enabling the development of innovative, environmentally friendly business models.

A substantial corpus of research has been published on the topic of textile waste recycling and its environmental benefits. The majority of these studies demonstrate that textile waste recycling has a lower environmental impact than traditional waste disposal methods (Espinoza-Pérez et al., 2024). Furthermore, research suggests that reuse is even more sustainable than recycling, as it extends product lifecycles and reduces the need for additional processing (Abagnato et al., 2024). However, a comprehensive evaluation of sustainability necessitates the consideration of emissions associated with RL. Absent consideration of the carbon footprint pertaining to transportation and logistics, the circular economy model may fall short in attaining its complete environmental potential. Consequently, the integration of effective RL strategies is imperative to ensure that circular economy solutions genuinely contribute to the fulfilment of sustainability objectives.

The European Commission has been actively developing legislation with the aim of promoting the circular economy (CE) and consequentially reverse logistics (RL). These strategies are key to reducing greenhouse gas emissions and optimizing resource efficiency. This commitment is illustrated by several key directives and action plans.

A notable policy, in addition to the above mentioned EPR, is the "Roadmap to a Resource Efficient Europe" (EU Commission, 2011), which outlines strategies to ensure the sustainable use and management of resources without compromising economic growth. Another pivotal initiative is the "Circular Economy Action Plan", aims to facilitate its implementation through collaboration with Member States, dedicated funding via cohesion policy funds, and support from the Horizon 2020 research and innovation framework programme (EU Commission, 2015; EU Commission, 2020). Additionally, Directive 2018/851 on Waste acknowledges the value of waste as a resource and underscores the benefits of enhancing waste management efficiency. The directive expressly acknowledges the potential of industrial symbiosis and encourages Member States to proactively facilitate its adoption (EU Commission, 2018). The European Commission's policies are thus intended to reinforce the transition towards a more sustainable, resource-efficient economic model.

In addition, the new Waste Shipments Regulation (EU) 2024/1157 came into force on 20 May 2024, introducing stricter controls over the international movement of textile waste. The aim of the regulation is to ensure that the export of waste, particularly textile waste, is managed in an environmentally sound manner. It explicitly prohibits the shipment of waste intended for disposal without prior authorization from the relevant authorities, thereby strengthening oversight across EU borders. Furthermore, under the new framework, non-OECD countries receiving textile waste must demonstrate that they have the necessary infrastructure and capabilities to handle and process the waste in accordance with recognized environmental standards. This regulation is a significant step forward in promoting circularity in the textile sector, encouraging greater responsibility for waste management within the EU and reducing the risk of environmental harm associated with improper disposal practices abroad.

Despite the European Commission's efforts to promote CE, it has been argued by some authors that sometimes, the existing regulations, can act as barriers due to their rigidity, lack of clarity, or inconsistencies (Simboli et al., 2015; lacondini et al., 2015).

A review by Biancolin et al. (2023) underscores the significance of integrating circular economy principles into RL planning. This integration has been shown to reduce the environmental impact of production processes whilst simultaneously enhancing corporate profitability. In addition, an effective RL planning has been demonstrated to create value for businesses by improving operational efficiency and strengthening competitive advantage, particularly as consumers increasingly favour products manufactured through sustainable practices (Vaz et al., 2013). Furthermore, RL aligns with the broader concept of "social responsibility in logistics," incorporating corporate social responsibility (CSR) principles into supply chain management. This ensures that companies address environmental and social concerns whilst maximising operational efficiency.

2.3 BARRIERS TO SUSTAINABLE RL

Despite the numerous benefits provided, RL also faces a range of challenges, which make this practice far to be widespread in the textile industry. The main reasons include high transport costs, up to 50-60% of the overall cost of RL (Parsa et al., 2020); several inefficiencies during collection and sorting; and many complications related to high recycling costs. Mallick et al. (2023) pointed out that there are three major obstacles in the adoption of reverse logistics and circular economy principles in textiles: organisational, financial, and political.

Organizational Barriers

Internal issues abound that hinder the complete integration of RL into business operations, since reverse logistics demands a system that can process a wide array of items under different conditions, which is logistically and financially challenging. One key issue is company policy, wherein companies often balk at the use of recycled materials due to perceived quality issues, thus limiting the reintegration of returned products into production or manufacturing lines (Witjes & Lozano, 2016). Besides, there are no standardized performance metrics to measure the effectiveness and performance of RL initiatives of companies. This situation is aggravated by a lack of training and skills development, which hampers the diffusion of RL practices in the industry (Moktadir et al., 2018). Finally, inadequacies regarding strategic planning inhibit companies from aligning RL goals with long-term business strategies, which will reduce the probability of sustainable success (Macchion et al., 2018).

Financial Barriers

The high costs associated with RL are also a major barrier, especially for those companies that lack the investment capacity in infrastructure, information technology infrastructure, and

personnel training. The effective handling of back textiles involves investing in processing, tracking, and remanufacturing systems, which most companies cannot justify (Jack et al., 2010). Without sufficient capital, companies are not able to scale up their RL activities, limiting them from closing the loop in apparel production.

[Policy Barriers](#)

Despite the increased government attention for circular economy approaches, inefficient and unclear policies still make it challenging to carry out RL (Chowdury & Hossain, 2015; Dangelico et al., 2013). Rising rapid fashion development has further worsened the issue by designing products that can survive for less time and further increasing apparel wasted, leading to increased needs for RL initiatives (Hyder et al., 2017). However, few government incentives and unclear policies prevent companies from adopting RL practices fully (McDowall et al., 2017).

[Addressing the Challenges](#)

To shatter these obstacles, it is fundamental to implement a mixed approach that includes investing in better sorting technology, sustainable transport solutions, and positive legislation. Cooperation with policymakers, businesses, and consumers can aid the implementation of recycling and enable circular economy principles to be more practical in the textile industry. Overcoming these challenges will allow the industry to cut waste, use resources more effectively, and develop more sustainable ways of producing goods.

2.4 RL IN THE MILITARY TEXTILE SECTOR

Given that Mascioni S.p.A. (the case study included in this research; see next section) is particularly active in the military textile market and that this sector is experiencing steady growth due to recent geopolitical developments and increased defence spending, it is essential to analyse the role of reverse logistics specifically in military textiles.

Military organisations manage large quantities of textile products – from uniforms and workwear to protective gear – that eventually reach end-of-life and require disposal or repurposing. Implementing reverse logistics in the military textile sector means establishing processes to retrieve these used textiles and reintegrate them into the value chain through reuse, recycling or proper disposal, thereby supporting circular economy objectives (Vasiliauskas et al., 2024). In practice, however, military reverse logistics systems are often not fully integrated or optimised for sustainability; recent research finds that while European armed forces do carry out reverse logistics activities (e.g. collection, repair, storage of used items), these efforts lack a unified strategy and frequently rely on outsourced civilian service providers (Vasiliauskas et al., 2024).

Nonetheless, there is growing momentum in Europe to close the loop on military textiles. The European Defence Action Plan of 2016 first called for circular economy principles to be transposed into the defence sector (Soufani et al., 2018), and more recently the European Defence Agency

(EDA) launched the Incubation Forum for Circular Economy in European Defence (IF CEED) to incubate projects on sustainable defence logistics, including textile waste recycling and valorisation. For example, one EDA-supported project is striving for a “*comprehensive conversion of military textile waste, transforming it into novel textile-based materials*” through an end-to-end recycling approach. Individual Member States’ militaries have also begun adopting circular practices for textiles. A notable case is the Netherlands’ armed forces, which recently ceased the routine incineration of old uniforms – a practice that had cost around €500,000 per year and wasted valuable material – and shifted to refurbishing, reissuing or recycling returned uniforms in partnership with private firms (Soufani *et al.*, 2018). As a result, approximately 750,000 used uniform items per year are now being sorted and prepared for reuse or material recycling instead of being destroyed (Soufani *et al.*, 2018). This kind of reverse-logistics initiative not only reduces waste and procurement costs, but also yields environmental benefits: a recent study calculated that recycling 200 kg of discarded military uniforms avoids nearly 489 kg of CO₂ emissions, whereas sending the same amount to incineration (without energy recovery) would *increase* emissions by over 400 kg (Huang *et al.*, 2025).

For companies like Mascioni S.p.A. – an Italian textile firm active in functional and military apparel markets – these developments underscore the importance of integrating robust reverse logistics strategies into the military textile supply chain. By designing uniforms and technical fabrics with end-of-life in mind and collaborating with defence agencies or recycling partners on take-back programs, the military textile sector can significantly enhance its sustainability profile. Reverse logistics in the military textile domain presents both a challenge and an opportunity: it requires overcoming logistical, security and technical hurdles (such as dealing with mixed-material uniforms and sensitive surplus gear), but it offers substantial payoffs in terms of waste reduction, resource savings and progress toward a circular economy in the defence field (Vasiliauskas *et al.*, 2024; Soufani *et al.*, 2018).

3. THE CASE STUDY

3.1 MASCIONI S.p.A.

Mascioni S.p.A. is an Italian textile company based in Cuvio, in the province of Varese, which has been active for over a century in the production and refinement of fabrics. Historically focused on home textiles and furniture, the company has in recent years diversified its portfolio, operating mainly in the military technical textile sector. This evolution has involved a transformation in both the materials used and the production processes, requiring an update of environmental management practices and logistics.

From the point of view of production, Mascioni clearly distinguishes two main areas: home textiles and military technical textiles.

In home textiles, the fabrics are made almost exclusively of 100% cotton, sometimes with a small percentage of linen on request from specific customers. The finishes applied to these fabrics are generally standard and aimed at improving the user experience and maintenance of the product: softening treatments, easy care to facilitate ironing, or anti-crease finishes.

Military technical textiles, on the other hand, use more complex composite materials, such as mixed cotton with polyamide, polyester or aramid fibres, depending on the specific performance required by the ministerial specifications. The finishes on these fabrics are more sophisticated and include water repellent, flame retardant and anti-infrared treatments, often combined. In some cases, Mascioni still uses fluorocarbons to guarantee certain performances, in derogation from the European regulations, as provided for by the technical specifications of military supplies. The diversity of materials and finishes has significant impacts on the recyclability of fabrics. Home textiles, being mono-fibre and treated with standard finishes, are more easily recoverable and can be reused, for example, as industrial rags or second-choice materials. Military technical fabrics, on the other hand, present greater difficulties of management at the end of life, due to the presence of mixed fibres, complex chemical treatments, accessories such as zippers and buttons, and stringent technical requirements that limit their possibilities for direct recycling.

Mascioni's revenue profile reveals a notable transformation between 2023 and 2024 in terms of both overall performance and the relative weight of its two primary business lines.

Graph 1: Mascioni's income of 2023 and 2024.

Total revenue increased from €23.5 million in 2023 to €25.5 million in 2024, marking growth of around 8.3%. However, this aggregate figure masks a significant internal rebalancing between the two product lines. The technical-military segment experienced remarkable growth, rising from €11.76 million in 2023 to €15.99 million in 2024. This rise translated into an increase in its share of total revenue, from 49.9% to 62.7%, thus consolidating its position as the primary driver of economic value within the company.

On the other hand, revenue from the home textiles segment fell from €11.79 million to €9.50 million, with its share of total earnings dropping from 50.1% to 37.3%. This trend reflects a broader strategic reorientation towards more specialised, high-value-added sectors, such as technical and military applications. This shift is likely influenced by market conditions, procurement cycles and product differentiation potential.

The shift in volume corroborates this interpretation. In terms of linear metres sold, the technical-military product line grew from 2.49 million metres in 2023 to 3.43 million metres in 2024, representing 38.9% of total metres sold (up from 25.4%). Conversely, the home line decreased from 7.31 million metres to 5.39 million metres, accounting for 61.1% of total volumes. This rebalancing implies a focus on market repositioning, materials, production intensity and end-of-life management, all of which are important for sustainability and circularity analysis.

From the point of view of environmental sustainability, Mascioni has adopted several initiatives to mitigate the impact of its production activity. The company independently operates a biological sewage treatment plant, operating since the seventies, which allows the treatment and partial reuse of water. In addition, Mascioni has converted its coal-fired power plant to biomass, using by-products from the understory from Lombardy and northern Italy. This move has allowed a more sustainable management of thermal energy, reducing the environmental impact and

exploiting local resources. To ensure the traceability and sustainability of this process, the company is completing a specific certification process for the use of biomass.

From the point of view of certifications, Mascioni currently holds OEKO-TEX Standard 100 certification and is working to achieve STeP by OEKO-TEX, focused on sustainable management of the entire production chain, and ISO 14001 certification for environmental management. These efforts reflect an increasing commitment to a structured approach to sustainability, even though the company does not yet publish a full sustainability report.

Regarding logistics, Mascioni uses mainly road transport since Cuvio is only reachable via road. About reverse logistics and the management of production waste, Mascioni does not carry out internal collection or recycling activities. The company's policy is oriented to minimize landfill and maximize recovery, relying on qualified operators who treat waste differently depending on the type of fabric. In some cases, the company has to bear costs for disposal; in others, it receives an economic compensation, although generally not significant, especially for more easily reusable materials.

Focus on military industry

Considering today's rapidly evolving geopolitical landscape, managing military textile waste has become a critical environmental and strategic challenge. As global tensions intensify and new conflicts arise, the defence sector across Europe is experiencing a surge in investment and production. This expansion is not only reshaping military capabilities but also amplifying the environmental implications of increased technical material consumption, including high-performance textiles used in uniforms, gear and protective equipment. This has direct implications for the European defence industry, which must adopt more environmentally friendly practices to minimise its environmental footprint and contribute to Europe's strategic autonomy. To support this transition, the European Defence Agency (EDA) is collaborating closely with the European Commission on a new 'Incubation Forum'. The initiative aims to encourage Member States to work together to develop cooperative project ideas that promote more circular and sustainable defence solutions (European Defence Agency, 2020).

According to the latest data released by the European Defence Agency (EDA) (2024), investment in the research, development and procurement of defence equipment reached unprecedented levels in 2023. Compared to the previous year, these investments increased by 17%, reaching a historic high of €72 billion — representing 26% of total defence expenditure. Forecasts for 2024 suggest this upward trend will persist, potentially surpassing €100 billion, which would account for over 30% of total defence spending. In 2023 alone, 22 EU Member States increased their defence expenditure, with 11 raising spending by over 10%, and one marking a staggering 50% increase in real terms.

The sustained growth of the defence sector implies a parallel increase in the production of military-specific textile items, which tend to be more robust, chemically treated and technically

complex than civilian garments. Unlike fast fashion garments, which dominate much of the literature on reverse logistics and are typically easier to disassemble or downcycle, military textiles present significant challenges due to their specialised coatings, multi-layered compositions and security-sensitive nature. These constraints usually lead to incineration or landfill as the main disposal methods, which significantly contribute to CO₂ emissions and the loss of resources (Hrab, 2024).

However, the high intrinsic value and technical potential of military textiles present an untapped opportunity. If these materials are properly recovered and reintegrated into the value chain, they could support both circular economy objectives and defence sustainability targets. Even within the military sector, there has been an increasing recognition of the need to identify the sustainable characteristics of goods and services. For instance, the U.S. Department of Defence (2018) emphasised the importance of sustainable procurement; however, specific operational guidelines for military uniforms are still lacking.

A compelling example of the implementation of a circular strategy comes from the Dutch Ministry of Defence. In 2017, they introduced a centralised procurement system for individual equipment, incorporating mechanisms for the recovery, repair, upgrading and recycling of used items. This initiative reduced the annual carbon footprint by 14,500 tonnes and generated approximately €750,000 in additional income, benefiting a workforce of around 60,000 soldiers (European Defence Agency, 2020).

In the first Coordinated Annual Review on Defence of 2020 (European Defence Agency, 2020), the European Commission (DG ENV) Director-General Florika Fink-Hooijer explicitly cites reverse logistics as a promising tool for circular implementation in defence, particularly in uniform management, remanufacturing and repair, with a strong emphasis on collaborating with private-sector partners to develop scalable, inclusive solutions. Companies that develop robust reverse logistics infrastructures tailored to the military sector could establish themselves as proactive contributors to national and European sustainability goals, while also opening up new market opportunities. For instance, recovered technical fibres could be reprocessed for secondary defence applications or transitioned to civilian technical uses. Establishing a regional textile recycling hub would address the growing waste issue, support traceability, and facilitate collaboration between defence institutions, research centres, and circular economy stakeholders, all working towards developing safe, innovative, and efficient processes for the valorisation of military-grade textiles.

3.2 MASCIONI'S SUSTAINABILITY PRACTICES AND THE CIRCULAR MANAGEMENT OF TEXTILE WASTE

To have a better understanding of Mascioni S.p.A.'s environmental and economic performance we acquired detailed operational data for 2023 and 2024. This data allows us to analyse the company's use of resources, its energy mix and its waste generation. This provides a solid foundation for evaluating circularity levels and identifying a range of key performance indicators (KPIs) to guide sustainability assessment and improvement.

3.2.1 Energy consumption

Firstly, a key performance indicator (KPI) is total annual energy consumption (kWh/year), which enables tracking of overall efficiency and energy intensity across production cycles. Another important KPI is the proportion of renewable energy in the total energy mix, reflecting the company's commitment to decarbonisation. Over the last two years, Mascioni has demonstrated a strong commitment to renewable energy, particularly with regard to thermal energy production. In 2024, the company consumed 14,481,604 kWh of thermal energy from natural gas, which is slightly down from 14,935,106 kWh in 2023. Significantly, however, the production of biomass-based thermal energy increased from 62,340,413 kWh in 2023 to 69,295,618 kWh in 2024. This shift meant that biomass covered 83% of total thermal energy in 2024, up from 81% the previous year — a tangible step towards decarbonisation and fossil fuel substitution.

Graph 2: Consumption of natural thermal energy and biomass thermal energy of 2023 and 2024.

Regarding electricity, the company reduced its reliance on externally purchased electricity, decreasing from 7,655,193 kWh in 2023 to 6,258,772 kWh in 2024. At the same time, internal electricity production increased from 6,450,000 kWh to 8,346,000 kWh, largely thanks to renewable energy sources. Consequently, internally produced electricity accounted for 57% of total electricity demand in 2024, up from 46% the previous year. These figures reflect improved energy autonomy and a reduction in the environmental impact associated with electricity procurement.

Graph 3: Comparison between electricity purchased and electricity produced in 2023 and 2024.

3.2.2 Water Consumption

Water use also represents a key aspect of circular resource management. Over the past two reporting periods, the total volume of water pumped into the system has decreased slightly from 1,551,533 m³ to 1,446,440 m³, suggesting a modest decrease in overall water usage. Concurrently, the volume of recirculated water increased from 471,533 m³ to 606,404 m³, resulting in a significant increase in the water recycling rate — from 23% to 30%. This improvement suggests a growing capacity for internal water reuse, which may be supported by more efficient treatment systems or process optimisation. However, when normalised to production output, water consumption per linear metre of fabric increased slightly from 0.158 to 0.164 m³/m, while water use per kilogram of product remained almost stable (0.431 to 0.426 m³/kg). These indicators suggest that, despite progress in recycling, overall water efficiency per unit of product has not yet improved substantially. This could reflect changes in the product mix, such as the production of more technically demanding or water-intensive fabrics. Going forward, reducing water

consumption per unit of output will be essential for improving environmental performance and aligning with sustainability targets.

3.2.3 CO₂ emissions

Mascioni S.p.A. has made considerable progress in reducing its Scope 1 CO₂ emissions thanks to a strategic shift in its energy mix. As the above figure shows, in 2019 the company's operations relied heavily on coal, resulting in around 41 million kilograms of CO₂ being emitted. Recognising the environmental and regulatory implications of such a carbon-intensive energy source, Mascioni began to decarbonise by transitioning to natural gas. This transition led to a significant reduction in emissions, which fell to approximately 15,5 million kilograms by 2021 — a decrease of around 62% compared to 2019 levels.

In 2022 the company took a decisive additional step towards renewable energy sources by adopting biomass. As a result, emissions fell further to around 2 million kg of CO₂, corresponding to a further 33% reduction compared to the previous year. This two-step transition demonstrates Mascioni's commitment to climate mitigation strategies and aligns with national decarbonisation goals and international climate targets.

Graph 4: CO₂ emissions in kg.

The shift from coal to natural gas and then to biomass reflects a broader sustainability strategy aimed at minimising the environmental footprint of textile production, particularly in energy-intensive processes such as dyeing and finishing. Furthermore, by reducing Scope 1 emissions —

those directly linked to fuel combustion within owned or controlled sources — the company improves its environmental reporting performance (e.g. ISPRA) and establishes itself as a responsible industry leader. These achievements also support the development of more circular and low carbon manufacturing models, thereby contributing to the business's long-term resilience and competitiveness.

3.2.4 Textile Waste Generation and Destination

A central pillar of this research is the analysis of textile waste generation, management and valorisation. Data reveals significant developments in the volume and disposal of waste produced by Mascioni, particularly textile waste. Waste-related KPIs provide additional insight into the circularity performance of Mascioni.

Total waste and Recovery Rates

A total of 741,613 kg of waste was generated in 2023, almost all of which (741,204 kg, or 99.9%) was sent for recovery. Just 409 kg were sent for disposal. This outstanding performance demonstrates near-complete circular handling of waste streams, likely through reuse, recycling or energy recovery processes.

However, the total waste generated increased significantly in 2024, reaching 1,090,800 kg (+47% year-on-year). At the same time, the proportion of waste sent for recovery fell to 74%, equating to 804,040 kg, while 286,760 kg — a much larger quantity than in 2023 — was sent for disposal. This downward trend raises important questions and highlights the need for a more in-depth investigation into the underlying causes. One possible explanation is the company's growing emphasis on the military-technical textile sector, which are more difficult to separate, recycle or process through conventional recovery channels.

Hazardous Waste

Furthermore, the proportion of hazardous waste that is managed in accordance with current regulations is an important indicator of compliance and environmental responsibility, particularly in industrial settings where chemical processes and finishing treatments are involved. In 2023, hazardous waste accounted for just 2,039 kg, representing 0.3% of the total waste generated. However, in 2024, this figure increased by over five times to 10,600 kg, raising its share to 1.0%. This increase could be due to a greater use of chemical-intensive treatments (e.g. coatings, dyes or flame retardants for technical fabrics), or to changes in classification and compliance with regulatory standards. From a sustainability and health perspective, managing hazardous waste poses additional challenges and requires more advanced handling protocols and traceability systems.

The logistic management of textile waste

To gain a deeper understanding of Mascioni S.p.A.'s approach to circularity, it is necessary to take a closer look at how the company manages textile waste in terms of both quantity and quality. Data from 2023 and 2024 provides detailed information on the volumes, types and destinations of textile waste, as well as the operational practices in place for its recovery.

When evaluating the circularity and sustainability performance of Mascioni S.p.A., it is essential to consider the management of textile waste. The company produces three main types of textile waste, each with different logistical and processing requirements: processed textile scraps (CER 040222), raw fabric waste (CER 040221) and textile dust and rags (also CER 040221, sub-categorised).

In 2023, Mascioni produced a total of 107,880 kg of textile waste. The majority of this (76,210 kg) consisted of processed textile scraps, which were transported in eight shipments, with an average load of 9,526 kg. Raw fabric waste accounted for 15,500 kg and was transported in four shipments. Finally, dust and rags totalled 16,170 kg and were transported in three deliveries, each averaging 5,390 kg.

The logistics routes for waste disposal in 2023 were relatively short. Specifically, raw fabric waste was delivered to a firm located just 18.5 km from Mascioni's facility. This minimised transport-related environmental impacts. Other types of waste were handled a waste management operator based 68 km away.

In 2024, the company recorded a significant decrease in total textile waste, with the figure falling to 77,960 kg — a reduction of 27.7% compared to the previous year. This improvement reflects positively on Mascioni's production efficiency and may be attributed to process optimisations, refined quality controls or a shift in product types and workflows.

Although the quantity dropped to 60,660 kg, processed textile scraps continued to represent the majority. Interestingly, there was a shift in waste logistics towards more frequent, smaller shipments, with an average load size of 5,515 kg across eleven deliveries. Meanwhile, raw fabric waste declined further to 10,690 kg across three shipments, while dust and rags were reduced to 6,610 kg and consolidated into just two deliveries.

The 2024 logistics network also saw a change in waste management partners. While the same firm of 2023 continued to handle raw fabric waste, the waste management operator became solely responsible for collecting and treating rags and dust. Meanwhile, the processing of textile scraps was assigned to a new operator which is located approximately 62 km away.

3.2.5 Estimation of CO₂ emissions from textile waste transport

In order to evaluate the environmental impact of transporting textile waste from Mascioni S.p.A., we calculated CO₂ equivalent (CO₂e) emissions based on distance travelled, number of shipments per year and standard emission factors per vehicle kilometre. The analysis considers the three main waste streams separately.

The methodology follows the official emission factors published by the UK Government in the 'GHG Conversion Factors for Company Reporting' (Department for Energy Security and Net Zero, 2025). These provide average CO₂e values per kilometre travelled depending on the vehicle category, size and load. Specifically, we made the following assumptions:

For loaded shipments, we applied the 'average laden' factor for:

- Rigid diesel trucks 3.5–7.5 tonnes: 0.49548 kg CO₂e/km.
- Rigid diesel trucks 7.5–17 tonnes: 0.60501 kg CO₂e/km.

For empty vehicles we used the respective 'empty' values:

- Rigid 3.5–7.5 tonnes: 0.46138 kg CO₂e/km
- Rigid >7.5–17 tonnes: 0.55061 kg CO₂e/km.

We evaluated each transport route by multiplying the distance between Mascioni's production site and the waste recipient by the number of trips recorded for each waste category. Where outward trips were presumed to be empty, their emissions were included to capture the environmental impact of the transport operation.

An analysis of CO₂e emissions from the transportation of textile waste reveals significant differences between 2023 and 2024. This sheds light on the impact of logistical decisions and shipment patterns on the environmental footprint of waste management activities.

In 2023, total transport-related emissions from textile waste amounted to around 935.22 kg of CO₂ equivalent, distributed across three main waste streams. Processed textile waste was the highest contributor, with 628.66 kg CO₂e generated over eight shipments over a distance of 68 km. Textile dust and rags, handled via three shipments, added another 235.75 kg CO₂e. Meanwhile, raw fabric waste, sent over a shorter distance of 18.5 km, accounted for the smallest share: 70.81 kg CO₂e.

In 2024, total emissions increased slightly to 998.40 kg CO₂e, despite a reduction in the total volume of textile waste generated. This shift is primarily due to changes in waste destinations and shipment frequency. Emissions from processed textile waste rose significantly, reaching 788.13 kg CO₂e — a 25.4% increase compared to the previous year. This increase is linked to the transition to a new collection partner which is located 62 km away, and an increase in the number of shipments from eight to 11, despite the average shipment size decreasing. Conversely, emissions from raw fabric waste fell to 53.11 kg CO₂e (down from 70.81 kg), driven by one fewer shipment in 2024. Emissions from textile dust and rags also fell to 157.16 kg CO₂e — a 33.3% decrease compared to 2023 — due to a reduction in shipments from three to two.

Overall, although Mascioni reduced the amount of textile waste generated in 2024, CO₂e emissions from transport increased by 6.8%. This increase is due to a more fragmented logistics configuration and longer or more frequent trips for certain waste categories. These findings highlight the importance of incorporating transport optimisation and emissions tracking into circular economy strategies, particularly since reducing waste alone may not necessarily lead to a lower environmental impact without a coordinated reverse logistics approach.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Analysis of data from 2023-2024 shows significant improvements in the environmental and economic performance of Mascioni S.p.A., particularly in terms of energy production from renewable sources, reduction of waste disposal and strengthening of its commercial position in the military technical sector.

In terms of energy, the company has increased its energy production from biomass, both thermal (from 81% to 83%) and electrical (from 46% to 57%), thereby reducing its dependence on fossil fuels. Water consumption has also become more efficient, with the proportion of recycled water increasing from 23% to 30% and CO₂ emissions decreased thanks to the used of biomass.

In economic terms, turnover increased by 8.3% (from €23.5 million to €25.5 million), driven particularly by the military technical sector, which increased its share of total turnover from 49.9% to 62.7%. This structural change is also reflected in sales volumes: linear metres sold in the military technical sector increased by 38%, while those in the home sector decreased by 26%.

Regarding waste, the 2024 figures show a significant increase in total waste produced (+47%), alongside a substantial reduction in the percentage of waste recovered (from 99.9% to 74%), and a notable rise in hazardous waste (+420%). However, regarding textile waste, there was a significant decrease in volumes delivered for recovery (-27.7%) and processed textile waste remains the most important category but has decreased by 20% compared to 2023.

In light of these emerging challenges, reverse logistics strategies could play a transformative role in restoring higher levels of material circularity and helping Mascioni to advance its environmental sustainability objectives. One particularly promising approach is the implementation of product take-back systems tailored specifically to the military-technical textile sector. Due to the durability and complexity of these fabrics, end-of-life products could be systematically returned to Mascioni for inspection, disassembly, and potential reprocessing, facilitating the recovery of valuable fibres or components. Such systems help to close material loops and strengthen Mascioni's position within the framework of extended producer responsibility (EPR).

From a logistics perspective, the military-technical textile sector usually has a concentrated ownership structure. A small number of institutional clients, such as industrial laundries or public service operators, hold large volumes of garments. These clients often manage entire fleets of uniforms or technical items which are subject to intensive use and standardised lifecycles. Consequently, when these products reach the end of their life, they tend to be returned or decommissioned in bulk, creating an opportunity for streamlined collection and reverse logistics operations. This centralised ownership and predictable disposal pattern makes the segment particularly well-suited to structured take-back programmes, batch-level sorting and coordinated recycling interventions, which could significantly improve material recovery rates and circularity outcomes.

An even more ambitious strategy would be to create a dedicated textile recycling hub. This facility could serve as a centralised platform for the aggregation, sorting, and treatment of pre- and post-consumer textile waste from not only Mascioni, but also other manufacturers in the local industrial district. By enabling economies of scale, such a hub would improve the efficiency and economic viability of recycling processes. Beyond its operational role, the hub could also function as a knowledge and innovation centre, fostering collaboration across the textile value chain, including with producers, recyclers, technology providers and academic institutions. Most importantly, establishing such a hub would enable textile waste to be given a new lease of life by reintegrating materials into the production cycle through reuse, upcycling or fibre-to-fibre recycling. This approach would reduce reliance on landfill sites and related CO₂ emissions, while contributing to the realisation of a circular economy in the textile sector where waste is treated as a valuable resource.

Another area worth exploring in collaboration with the company is the integration of blockchain-based traceability systems within the reverse logistics network. Such technology could facilitate the secure and transparent exchange of data regarding the origin, composition, and processing history of textile materials, from production to reuse or recycling. This level of traceability would facilitate compliance with emerging EU regulations on digital product passports and sustainable textile labelling and could strengthen stakeholder trust and open new avenues for certified circular products.

These strategies reflect a shift from ad hoc waste management to a proactive, system-level circular economy model where waste is reimagined as a resource and reverse logistics becomes a core business enabler rather than a peripheral function. For Mascioni, engaging in such a transformation could mitigate environmental impacts and generate a competitive advantage through innovation, resilience and sustainability leadership. The collaboration with this company is planned to continue also after the conclusion of the NODES research project, in order to better understand the feasibility of the above cited innovations to reverse logistics supporting the circular economy transition and enhancing the sustainability of the whole supply chain.

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